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Subversive Voices: Piro's Poetry and the Politics of Language, Gender, and Resistance in 19th-Century Punjab

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Abstract:

Piro, a 19th-century courtesan-turned-poet, occupies a radical space in Punjabi literary history through her defiance of patriarchal, religious, and linguistic hierarchies. As a marginalised woman navigating multiple identities – concubine, poet, and dissenter – her writings challenge hegemonic discourses that sought to silence female agency. This paper examines how Piro's poetry embodies cultural plurality through its linguistic hybridity, drawing on elements from Punjabi, Persian, and Braj Bhasha to articulate a voice of resistance. Her work not only disrupts the normative moral codes imposed upon women but also critiques institutionalised religious authority, particularly the Udasi sect. By positioning herself as both subject and storyteller, Piro reclaims female desire, honour, and self-determination in a literary landscape that often erased women's voices. Through an intertextual and feminist lens, this study examines how Piro's narrative engages with broader themes of gender, power, and cultural negotiation in colonial Punjab. Her poetry serves as a powerful testament to the pluralistic and contested spaces of language, literature, and identity, offering a crucial intervention in South Asian literary and feminist historiography.

Keywords: Piro, Punjabi poetry, courtesan, linguistic hybridity, gender and resistance, female agency, cultural plurality, religious authority, colonial Punjab.

Piro (c. 1810-12 – 1872) emerges as a radical and subversive voice in nineteenth-century Punjabi literature, embodying a spirit of rebellion that transcended conventional societal norms. Her defiance extended beyond mere rejection of patriarchy, encompassing repudiation of caste, religion, and gender-based constraints. As a courtesan-turned-poet and a convert to the heterodox Gulabdasi sect, she not only defied the rigid moral, social, and religious codes imposed on women but also resisted the hegemonic forces that sought to erase female agency from literary and historical discourse. Despite her significant contributions, she remained largely neglected in Punjabi literary historiography for almost a century after her death. The absence of scholarly evaluation concerning Piro's poetry is no coincidence, rather, it is underpinned by multifaceted historical, ideological, and profound psychological factors, contributing to the oversight of her literary contributions by researchers, critics, and historians of Punjabi literature (Sirsa 13).

This marginalisation is exemplified in Piara Singh Padam's dismissal of her authorship in his book *Kalam De Chamatkar* (1981): "One siharfi is found under the name of Piro *kanjari*, another in collaboration with Bawa (Gulab Das). Some researchers proclaim her to be the first female poet of Punjabi. It is not true. Many poets lived with Bawa; he was a poet himself. If someone in jest related a siharfi to Piro's name or wrote it under Piro's name, it does not make Piro a poet (296)." This scepticism underscores how Piro's authorship was systematically undermined, despite the undeniable presence of her autobiographical *Ik Sau Sath kafian (160 Kafis)* - a rare instance of self-representation by a woman in nineteenth-century Punjab. She asserted her creative agency and carved out a space for female self-representation within a largely male literary tradition. Written in a distinct voice and vernacular idiom, it offers a compelling narrative of resistance, detailing her journey from Lahore's Hira Mandi to the unconventional spiritual commune of Chathanwala

(Kasur), and illuminating the plural registers of language, gender identity, and dissent in colonial Punjab.

Piro's life remains largely undocumented except through her poetic autobiography, *Ik Sau Sath Kafian*, which details her experiences from Lahore to Chathianwala. However, it provides no insight into her familial background or early upbringing, leaving scholars completely dependent on oral history and folk narratives (Sirsa 15). Popular opinion estimates her birth around 1810-1812 in Gujranwala. Her caste background is ambiguous; some sources claim she belonged to a middle-class Muslim farming family, while others suggest she identified as a Dalit, frequently referring to herself as a shudra (Vidyarthi 7; Bal 185; Shaharyar 9). This designation could reflect either her true social status or her attempt to highlight the low status of women in society (Bal 185-186). Legend holds that her birth, following a long period of her parents' childlessness, was perceived as a divine blessing by Sufi saints, leading to her name Peeranditi, potentially a short form of Perunissa or Perbano (Vidyarthi 7). As an only child, she faced early adversity with her mother's untimely death during her formative years, which left lasting emotional scars. Her father was religious; saints, fakirs, and pirs often visited their home, leaving an everlasting influence on her. She received an elementary education from a local mauvi. Her life took a dramatic turn when she eloped at a young age, infatuated with a holy man. After his death, a few years later, she found herself alone in an unfamiliar environment and sought refuge in a brothel, where she learned to sing and dance, ultimately becoming a star performer in Hira Mandi, Lahore. (Bal 185-186)

Piro's *Ik Sau Sath Kafian* narrates her journey from Lahore to Chathianwala - her encounter with Gulab Das (1809-1873), her decision to become his disciple, her return from Chathianwala, subsequent imprisonment, and eventual escape facilitated by her guru, Gulab Das. She first encountered Gulab Das in Lahore's Moti Bazar, where he came to deliver a sermon and became

his disciple. Gulab Das was a dissentient advaitin (monist) guru from a Sikh sectarian background, residing with his disciples in the socially unconventional and literarily flourishing environs of Chathianwala village, Kasur. He was a learned man and an independent-minded guru who defied the rules of conventional morality and varnashrama dharma. (Piro & the Gulabdasis 17, 45). Her decision to become his disciple faced strong opposition from her guardians, who, according to some sources, brought her back from Chathianwala to Lahore. However, according to Giani Gian Singh and Mahant Ganesha Singh, she was taken back to Gujranwala instead of Lahore - *akhir gye Gujranwale varis tis ko lai hain* (1220).

This incident of bringing Piro back from Chathianwala and the attempt of her guardians to reintegrate her into Islam was provoked by Ilahi Baksh, a prominent general under Maharaja Ranjit Singh who commanded his artillery and was an admirer of her. Piro's refusal to come back into the fold of Islam and her heated argument with the *kazi* are recorded in her autobiographical 160 kafian. Her steadfast refusal to accept Shara led to her imprisonment in Wazirabad, where she befriended two women, Jaano and Rehmati, who sent a missive to Gulab Das. He then sent two disciples, Chatar Singh and Gulab Singh (Kala Singh in some sources), to rescue her. Piro describes her rescue fantastically, claiming that the locks fell at her touch and the guards and pursuers were struck blind as they escaped. Piro remained with Gulab Das until she died in 1872. Although they never married, their intimate relationship is well documented. Giani Gian Singh claims they lived abhed (inseparably), and Mahant Ganesha Singh notes their shared belief in yoga and bhog. Gulab Das died six months later and, according to his will, was buried in the same grave as Piro (Swarajbir 106-107, Gyan Singh 1220, Ganesha Singh 128).

Nineteenth-century Punjab was characterised by rigid gender norms, where women were expected to conform to ideals of modesty, domesticity, and religious piety. Social structures, reinforced by

both Sikh and Islamic traditions, placed strict moral boundaries on women's roles, rendering female voices largely invisible in literary and historical records (Bal 184). In this context, Piro's poetry emerges as a radical intervention, subverting dominant discourses through its linguistic hybridity, critique of institutionalised religion, and assertion of female autonomy. By blending Punjabi and Braj Bhasha, her work defies linguistic hierarchies, positioning itself outside the dominant literary frameworks of her time. This paper argues that Piro's poetry not only disrupts patriarchal and religious narratives but also serves as an assertion of selfhood, honour, and desire in a society that sought to suppress such expressions. In her *Ik Sau Sath Kafian*, she makes use of her language and art of storytelling to reclaim agency and gives voice to female experience. Through close textual analysis, this study examines *Ik Sau Sath Kafian* to explore how her work engages with broader themes of gender, power, and cultural negotiation, ultimately reclaiming a space for women's voices.

Piro lived at the intersection of the medieval rule of Maharaja Ranjit Singh and the beginning of colonialism in Punjab under the British. The linguistic landscape was deeply shaped by a complex interplay of languages, each carrying distinct cultural and social significance. Persian, as the official language of administration and Islamic scholarship, symbolised power and authority, while Braj Bhasha held a prestigious position within Sikh and Bhakti literary traditions, widely used in religious and philosophical discourse. Punjabi, the most commonly spoken vernacular, was often marginalised in formal literary circles. Piro's poetry, composed in Gurmukhi script heavily influenced by Braj, strategically blended these linguistic traditions to challenge dominant narratives. Piro's linguistic and formal choices further distinguish her from her male contemporaries, who often maintained a philosophical or allegorical distance from their personal experiences and explored spiritual or cultural themes without foregrounding their autobiographies.

Piro's work, *Ik Sau Sath Kafian*, is a juxtaposition of convention and innovation. The style and language of her work indicate the massive influence of the Gulabdasi sect on her writing, as well as on her literacy and training in poetry and philosophy. She composed her *kafis* - a six-line format with a simple metrical pattern where the last words of every two lines rhyme - in Gurmukhi script influenced by Braj. The use of Gurmukhi script and Braj language was a common heritage of Sikh sects, the former being popularised by Guru Arjan Dev Ji and the latter by Guru Gobind Singh Ji. Piro used this traditionally non-narrative genre, akin to a ghazal in its lack of narrative sequence, to tell her own story. Instead of the popular Punjabi narrative tradition of Qissa, which focuses on revered cultural stories rather than personal accounts, Piro adapted the kafi to narrate her life. She skillfully arranged various tales and used her rhetorical abilities to craft her narrative. Kafis are rhyming verses popular among the Sufis of Punjab. They are not typically narrative, but Piro's *Ik Sau Sath Kafian* bent this rule. Piro's kafian is in the *siharfi* format, where each verse traditionally starts with the next letter of the Perso-Arabic alphabet, however, she did not follow the alphabet and deliberately deviated from its rigid structure to express her autonomy as a poet and paved her way as a woman in the lack of strong tradition of writers in the Punjabi Literature. (Bhakti & the Gendered Self 7-8).

In contrast to poets like Bulle Shah and Waris Shah, who used linguistic hybridity within allegorical and mystical themes, Piro made use of direct and personal resistance in her poetry. Her *Ik Sau Sath Kafian* is not the usual compilation of philosophical reflections, moral teachings, or advice on leading a devotional life, but a means of self-justification, crafted to lay to rest the doubts surrounding her transition from a courtesan to a disciple of the Gulabdasi sect. She created a linguistic and literary space where her defiant voice could resonate across social and religious boundaries. Her rhetorical skill allowed her to challenge rumours and defend her agency, making

her poetry both a personal testament and a public declaration of resistance. It allowed her to clarify, justify, and promote her version of events, while also dispelling the harmful rumors that arose from her unprecedented move, which not only affected her but also cast aspersions on her guru (“Telling her tale?” 543).

Anshu Malhotra, in her book *Piro and the Gulabdasis* (2017), calls her an “exceptional normal” woman, claiming that she was not a ‘woman worthy’, nor yet an ‘everywoman’. She inhabited multiple marginalised positions: a courtesan, she identified herself as a ‘shudra vesva’ (a low-caste prostitute), a term reflecting her low-caste status and the societal constraints she faced. Living in a society with strict gender hierarchies, she further challenged norms by entering a monastic establishment where women were not entirely welcome. Additionally, as a Muslim among the Gulabdasis - a sect situated between Hinduism and Sikhism - she was acutely aware of her religious crossing and the ambivalent status it brought.

Her life in the borderlands gave her a unique liminal status. She lived between social respectability and unacceptability, sexual promiscuity as a prostitute, and sexual containment as a ‘mother’ to the Gulabdasi disciples. She also navigated between Hinduism, Sikhism, and Islam. This precarious existence allowed her to see the emptiness of moral and ritualistic religious practices, which she often critiqued. Positively, her background as a courtesan likely endowed her with musical and poetic skills, and possibly basic literacy, which she refined with the Gulabdasis. These skills enabled her to engage with the literariness that was central to the Gulabdasis. Her marginality instilled her life with a sense of desperation, driving her to seek new ways of living and being. She relied on her instincts, agency, and a strong sense of self-possession and confidence to navigate her complex existence (17-22).

From a feminist theoretical perspective, Piro's poetry can be read as a subversion of traditional gender roles. She rejects the prevalent virtue prescribed for females. Patriarchal discourse relegated women to passive roles. Piro actively reclaims her identity, portraying herself not as a victim but as an agent of her destiny. Her descriptions of captivity, escape, and ultimate spiritual fulfilment serve as metaphors for a woman's struggle. She emerges as a bold woman who asserts her autonomy in a world that sought to confine her to traditional roles. In one of her *kafis*, she challenges the authority of religious figures who sought to "reform" her, instead asserting her own spiritual path as valid and self-determined. By doing so, she resists both the societal condemnation of her past as a courtesan and the patriarchal gatekeeping of religious spaces. Her affiliation with the Gulabdasis further complicates traditional gendered binaries. Gulabdasis is a male-dominated sect, but it provided her with the literacy and philosophical grounding to express her defiance in poetic form. Piro's unique voice, sometimes imbued with rage and sometimes with devotional longing, illustrates how women on the margins could carve out spaces of empowerment. Her writings resonate with the ethos of *bhakti*, a devotional movement that historically allowed women greater access to spiritual expression, yet she transforms *bhakti* into a personal and political act of resistance. Her poetry critiques the hollowness of ritualistic religious practices. It redefines devotion as an inclusive space where gender does not dictate spiritual worth. She offers a striking counter-narrative to the erasure of female desire and self-assertion in traditional literature. Her resistant voice in the poetry defied caste, gender, and religious constraints.

Piro's poetry is a scathing attack on religious authority, particularly the hypocrisy of religious leaders. She threw light on Bhakti and Sufi traditions to expose how orthodox religious institutions manipulated doctrine to serve the powerful, and on the other hand, restricted the spiritual agency of marginalised women. In her poetry, she condemns the rigid formalism of qazis, pandits, and

Sikh leaders alike. These ritualistic religious heads ignored true spirituality. Her sharp verses, such as “*Qazis trapped the Turks in the honour of the Koran, Hindus are tricked by the pandits who read the Vedas to them*” (K.152), reveal her deep frustration with religious orthodoxy. Her thought is one with poets like Kabir and Bulleh Shah, who similarly denounced ritualistic religion. Like Kabir’s rejection of sectarian divides with “*na ham Hindu na Musalman*” (I am neither Hindu nor Muslim), Piro challenges religious divides.

Piro’s dissenting stance places her within a broader tradition of socio-religious reformers in South Asia. Her work resonates with the Bhakti movement’s radical low-caste figures like Kabir and Ravidas. However, Piro’s voice is uniquely gendered, unlike these male poets, she directly addresses the exclusion of women from religious institutions and rituals. She highlighted the absurdity of male-centric initiation practices in Sikhism with lines like “*A woman does not wear drawers—what will they do?*” (K.136). Her poetry also reminds of Bulleh Shah’s subversion of religious dogma through irony and wit, as seen in his critique of blind faith in scriptures: “*Ved Quranan parh-parh thake*” (We are tired of reading the Vedas and the Quran). Yet, Piro extends this tradition by placing women’s experiences at the center of her spiritual inquiry. She uses figures like Ganika and Kubja to argue for female inclusion in divine grace. Her verses challenged contemporary religious authorities and contributed to the broader movements of spiritual reform that questioned caste, gender, and institutionalised religion. Here, it is important to note that her unique contribution was overlooked in Punjab's history of religious dissent (Piro 82-114).

Piro’s work engages deeply with feminist literary traditions. It challenges patriarchal order through intertextuality and self-representation. She brings in the voices of Hir and Sita as marginalised females from vastly different cultural and religious traditions. Reinterpretation of their narratives highlights the gendered oppression. Bulleh Shah and Shah Hussain subverted the trope of Hir to

articulate spiritual longing, Piro uses Hir's voice to confront religious authorities. She exposes the male-centric discourse and hypocrisy in controlling female sexuality. Similarly, by positioning herself as Sita, she presents the paradox of being both a marginalised and morally righteous woman. She tries to regain her agency in a society that defines her based on her past as a courtesan. Her intertextuality places her in the high position of feminist literary traditions that challenge dominant narratives by inserting female perspectives into canonical stories. Like Andal and Mirabai, who defied social norms through their devotion to the divine, Piro, too, constructs an identity that transcends traditional expectations of femininity. However, unlike Mirabai, whose defiance led to isolation, Piro's strategic alignment with Bhakti traditions allowed her to secure an authoritative role within the dera, transforming her from an outcast to a revered consort and spiritual mother figure (Bhakti & the Gendered Self 12-43).

Piro's poetry exemplifies what Julia Kristeva describes as intertextual resistance, where texts interact to subvert dominant ideologies. She draws from religious and folk traditions to reconfigure the notion of female devotion. She shifted the concept of devotion from passive submission to active self-assertion. Like Ambapali in Buddhist traditions or Mary Magdalene in Christianity, Piro's journey from prostitution to spiritual redemption carries symbolic weight. Her poetry thus stands as an early feminist intervention.. Through intertextual borrowing and rewriting of patriarchal narratives, Piro critiques and reshapes the literary and spiritual landscape of her time.

Piro's poetry blends multiple linguistic traditions in the nineteenth century. It subverts the established poetic forms through her literary dialogues with figures like Hir, Sita, and Mirabai. Her work reshapes the literary canon by asserting the legitimacy of female self-representation. Piro emerges as an early feminist figure whose contributions remain crucial in understanding the intersections of gender, language, literature, and resistance in Punjabi literary history.

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